

STEPHEN KRASHEN'S METHOD WILL HELP YOU LEARN ANY LANGUAGE

Nabieva Yulduz

Teacher of the Syrdarya Regional Law School

G-mail: Yulduznabiyeva1@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This article will analyze the input hypothesis, one of the five hypotheses that formed Stephen Krashen's Monitor Model, which in turn served as the theoretical basis of the natural approach method. The article will provide an overview of the main provisions of the hypothesis, as well as practical pedagogical advice for teachers of foreign languages. Stephen Krashen's Monitor Model is one the most ambitious theories of the second language studying process. Krashen has argued that his account provides a general or overall theory of the second language acquisition with important implications for language teaching.

Introduction.

Language acquisition does not require extensive use of conscious grammatical rules, and does not require tedious drill. Acquisition requires meaningful interaction in the target language - natural communication - in which speakers are concerned not with the form of their utterances but with the messages they are conveying and understanding.

It has been scientifically proven that the brain has amazing plasticity, and if it is trained in a certain way, it "grows" the neural connections necessary to master a certain subject. Neurobiologist Sandrine Turet, based on her research, states that with regular training, a person can create neurons of the desired characteristics and quality in the brain. You should always do this to learn any foreign language or to

acquire any knowledge. If you work on a task without interruption, the result will not wait for you. But how?

To learn foreign languages, a person must have the ability to think logically and analyze information. If you can easily understand physical and chemical formulas or programming theory, then you should have no problems with literacy or essay writing, as both are just usability skills. All you need is to learn another language. One should not refuse to study a complex subject because of lack of inclination for it, on the contrary, one should constantly engage in it.

The Acquisition/ Learning Hypothesis. According to Krashen, there are two ways to acquire a foreign language: assimilation and learning. The first process happens unconsciously: you receive knowledge on a

subconscious level without specifically learning anything. That is, assimilation is similar to how a child learns his/her mother tongue: he learns the literal meaning of the word and does not learn it deliberately. When reading English, listening to music, watching movies, you are doing assimilation. To learn a foreign language, you create a language environment around you. According to Krashen, assimilation is more effective than learning, so when learning a new language, more time should be devoted to its natural perception rather than mechanical learning.

The Monitor Hypothesis. Strongly related to the first hypothesis, the Monitor Hypothesis explains how acquired and learned language are used in speech production. So, according to Krashen, we begin to speak and write in the language we are learning because of assimilation. Why study? Learning begins the emergence of an "internal editor" that controls the literacy of our speech. At the same time, Krashen writes, language barriers appear in people who spend more time studying than learning the language. This is logical: a person begins to be afraid of making mistakes, controls himself too much and, as a result, does not dare to speak the language he is learning.

The Natural Order of Acquisition Hypothesis. Based on the findings of Dulay and Burt (1974, 1975), Krashen (1982) claims that language rules and grammatical structures are acquired in a predictable, natural, and necessary order, which underlines the previous claim of acquisition being more central to second language learning, since a 'natural order' is "a result of the acquired system" (Gass and Selinker, 2001, p.199) and independent of

instruction. This hypothesis causes the most controversy among linguists. According to Krashen, any person learns any language in a certain natural order. That is, no teacher can change the order of mastering the material. For example, when learning English, any person first learns general questions (can be answered with yes / no) and only then specific questions. This hypothesis, on the other hand, is aimed at teachers, whom Krashen called on not to reinvent the wheel, not to experiment with the sequence of language learning, but to present materials according to the principle from simple to complex.

The Input hypothesis. According to Krashen, assimilation of a foreign language occurs when a student perceives the material he understands by ear or by sight: listening to podcasts, watching series, reading texts. However, material at a level above the student's current level will provide maximum benefit. It should be noted that good textbooks are based on this principle: you study the material one step harder than your level. Evidences for the input hypothesis can be found in the effectiveness of caretaker speech between an adult to a child, of a teacher's talk to a language student, or in a sympathetic conversation partner to a language learner/acquirer. One of the assertions of this hypothesis is that language students should be given an initial «silent period», where they are building up acquired competence in a language before they begin to produce it.

The Affective Filter Hypothesis. Perhaps the most interesting hypothesis. According to Krashen, the emotional filter is a kind of screen that prevents language acquisition and learning. At the same time,

to a greater extent, this screen harms natural absorption. An emotional filter appears in a person experiencing negative emotions: fear, anger, irritation, sadness, etc. According to the hypothesis, the screen is responsible for the brain's natural assimilation of material does not allow knowledge to reach the part. Stress, lack of motivation, self-doubt, etc. contribute to the appearance of an emotional filter.

Based on the theoretical and practical research in order to provide an optimal input of the information, we suggest that foreign language class curriculum should contain the following elements:

- Use of an original approach to presentation and practice of the language material;
- Teaching the art and strategies of communication before grammar;
- Encouraging speaking from the very first class;
- Helping to overcome psychological barriers;
- Helping develop memory and imagination;
- Ensuring fast and durable memorizing of considerable amounts of language material;

- Teaching the art of communication;
- Stimulating cognitive processes in the student;
- Preventing fatigue or monotony in the learning process.

As communication is not only the aim but also the means of the language teaching, it requires group learning as opposed to individual tuition. Any course should aim at developing the student's learning potential, his/her hidden capacities.

Conclusion

Some researchers believe that children are inherent in assimilation, while adults are characterized by learning. However, adults can also acquire language, an ability that persists throughout life. Error correction is not useful in learning, but is important in learning because it helps the learner to understand and internalize the rule. From Stephen Krashen's point of view, learning is secondary, less important than mastering. McLaughlin (1987) agrees saying that Krashen merely demonstrates how "certain phenomena can be viewed from the perspective of his theory" (p. 36).

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